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Abstract

Objective: The main objective of this research is the design and implementation of a new fuzzy logic tool for automatic drug delivery in patients undergoing general anesthesia. The aim is to adjust the drug dose to the real patient needs using heuristic knowledge provided by clinicians. A two-level computer decision system is proposed. The idea is to release the clinician from routine tasks so that he can focus on other variables of the patient. **Methods:** The controller uses the Bispectral Index (BIS) to assess the hypnotic state of the patient. Fuzzy controller was included in a closed-loop system to reach the BIS target and reject disturbances. BIS was measured using a BIS VISTA monitor, a device capable of calculating the hypnosis level of the patient through EEG information. An infusion pump with propofol 1% is used to supply the drug to the patient. The inputs to the fuzzy inference system are BIS error and BIS rate. The output is infusion rate increment. The mapping of the input information and the appropriate output is given by a rule-base based on knowledge of clinicians. **Results:** To evaluate the performance of the fuzzy closed-loop system proposed, an observational study was carried out. Eighty one patients scheduled for ambulatory surgery were randomly distributed in 2 groups: one group using a fuzzy logic based closed-loop system (FCL) to automate the administration of propofol (42 cases); the second group using manual delivering of the drug (39 cases). In both groups, the BIS target was 50. **Conclusions:** The FCL, designed with intuitive logic rules based on the clinician experience, performed satisfactorily and outperformed the manual administration in patients in terms of accuracy through the maintenance stage.

Keywords Knowledge-based system; fuzzy control; intelligent devices; drug delivery; anesthesia

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In this new version, we have taken into account all the valuable comments and suggestions of both reviewers. Now, we believe that this new version of the manuscripts has increased its quality. The main changes driven are the following ones:

- We have included some new references in order to improve the Discussion section as well as to consider latest papers based on recent research.
- We have added some extra information about the Fuzzy Logic Controller (FLC) developed to improve the previous explanation.
- A new figure (Figure 7) has been included in order to show graphically the results of the experimental trials for the 42 patients involved in the FCL group.
- All the minor changes suggested by the reviewers were also included.

The detailed changes for each reviewer are summarized below:

Reviewer 3

First of all, we want to thank the very helpful comments of the reviewer 3. We have tried to answer all the comments and suggestions as follows:

I think the authors should include and discuss the formerly cited paper (“A multiobjective design of a patient anaesthetist-friendly neuromuscular blockade controller” Fazendeiro P, de Oliveira JV, Pedrycz W) in order to better frame their work within the current state-of-art.

As suggested by the reviewer, we have included this reference in the Discussion section of the manuscript. Also, in this section we included a new paragraph to discuss some aspects related to this.

Fazendeiro’s proposal is a very interesting solution to approach a very similar problem related to the anesthesia control. Through several optimization techniques, a fuzzy controller was developed taking into account patients intervariability. Also, a design of a decision rule-based protocol to explain the undertaken control decision that lies behind the neuromuscular blockade is presented. However, there are some striking differences that should be highlighted:

- From the clinical point of view, it is easier to measure the effects of atracurium by noninvasive methods (TOF or kinemyography) than the hypnotic effects in patients*. Furthermore, the influence of inter-intraindividual pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamics variability of propofol, pharmacogenetic aspects, changes in blood and plasma volume as well as the variable intensity of surgical stimulus turn the control of hypnosis into a harder problem. What is more, although propofol

effect could be critically affected by the interaction with remifentanyl (analgesic agent), neuromuscular blockade is not affected by another drug actions**.

- From the control problem point of view, both solutions highly differ from each other. The main objective in Fazendeiro's research is not only the development of a controller but also the design of a decision rule based protocol to explain the undertaken control decision behind the neuromuscular blockade process. The lack of knowledge behind the neuromuscular scenario turns the use of several optimization strategies into a very suitable solution as it automatically generates the membership functions as well as the required rules. However, our starting point is different. We consider the heuristic knowledge of clinicians and their expertise obtained through different real decisions made to design the rules as well as the membership functions. In this sense, the proposed controller takes advantage of the main purpose of fuzzy logic theory: translation of the knowledge in a natural language into an automatic algorithm capable of being managed by clinicians.
- It is important to notice that although good results have been reached by Fazendeiro in simulation, no clinical trials were performed to study the suitability of the controller in the clinical real stage. Our experience in hundreds of real time trials with patients shows that there are several inevitable challenges in the real anesthetic and surgical environment that cannot be reproduced using a model with a noise component. However, our controller has shown that is capable to deal with different uncertainties in real practice.

In light of the above, Fazendeiro's proposal, as well as some other solutions previously researched such as the use of ANFIS algorithm, could be suitable when there is a lack of knowledge behind the process to design a fuzzy logic controller. However, it is a fact that

the acquisition of rules and the design of the controller based on heuristic knowledge involves a rigorous pre-study to consider all the situations mentioned above. In this sense we consider that our proposal tackles a difficult problem involving the presence of different variables taking into account the expertise of physicians.

* *LE Guen M1, Liu N, Chazot T, Fischler M. Closed-loop anesthesia. Minerva Anesthesiol. 2016 May;82(5):573-81. Epub 2015 Nov 10.*

** *Bouillon TW, Bruhn J, Radulescu L, Andresen C, Shafer TJ, Cohane C, Shafer SL Pharmacodynamic interaction between propofol and remifentanyl regarding hypnosis, tolerance of laryngoscopy, bispectral index, and electroencephalographic approximate entropy Anesthesiology. 2004 Jun; 100(6):1353-72.*

Reviewer 4

First of all, we want to thank the very helpful comments of the reviewer 4. We have tried to answer all the comments and suggestions as follows:

Figure 2, Δv has a fuzzy label that is isolated from the others, using such membership function can result in discontinuity.

This is an interesting issue that needs to be explained. Infusion rate increment (Δv) is the output of our system. The triangular membership function on the left side is considered as a “special emergency” Membership Function. If ΔBIS is highly negative (BIS decreases very quickly) or BIS value is under safety limits, the remifentanyl infusion rate must be highly decreased.

Moreover, it is important to note that the Mamdani System proposed in our research uses a defuzzification process through the Centre of Area method. As a matter of fact, all the values within the Universe of Discourse can be reached although some membership functions are not overlapped. It is shown in Image 5 (Response surface of the fuzzy controller). Δv strongly decreases when $BIS_e(t)$ is very negative. However, it is shown that it does not result in discontinuity but in a progressive change of rate decrement.

We included this explanation in the original text to improve the clarity of this section.

Delta_BIS is active in the range of -3 to +3, the rest is saturation, what is the benefit of doing that?

Once we studied the different data captured from real surgeries to design the Fuzzy Inference System, it was shown that the BIS change input (ΔBIS) did not reach values over ± 2 . That is why we decided to saturate the rest of the values along the Universe of

Discourse. Moreover, once we tested the developed Fuzzy Controller over the real patients, all the ΔBIS input values during the surgery reached values within the ± 2 range. We have decided to include this explanation in the original text in order to make it easy to understand for readers.

Ref 2, publication year is missing.

The publication year of reference 2 has been included.

The work included experimental trials on many patients, only one shown in figure 6, other cases should be shown as this is important results.

As suggested by the reviewer, we have added a new figure (figure 7) in order to include the information not only for one patient but also for the others in the FCL group. We decided to show the information of the median, 10th and 90th percentile for 20 minutes once the automatic control task had started (after manual bolus infusion). We think that it is a good way to summarize the behaviour of the 42 patients enrolled in the FCL group for this study.

Some equations in the text, the use of X as a multiplication sign is not correct, please use proper math symbols.

We have corrected this point.

Please, update the references list to include latest papers, it is clear that the paper has been in review for a considerable period of time, hence the references are dated to 2016 latest.

According to the reviewer's suggestion, we have included the following references:

- Pota M, Esposito M, De Pietro G. Designing rule-based fuzzy systems for classification in medicine. *Knowledge-based Systems*. 2017. Volume 124. 105-132.
- Arıkan FGO, Turan G, Özgültekin A, Sivrikaya Z, Cosar BC, Onder DN. Rocuronium: automatic infusion versus manual administration with TOF monitorisation. *Journal of Clinical Monitoring and Computing*. 2016. Vol. 30, Issue 5: 545-550.
- Padula F, Ionescu C, Latronico N, Paltenghi M, Visioli A, Vivacqua G. Optimized PID control of depth of hypnosis in anesthesia. *Computer methods and programs in biomedicine*. 2017. Vol.144, pp. 21-35.
- Merigo L, Beschi M, Padula F, Latronico N, Paltenghi M, Visioli A. Event-Based control of depth of hypnosis in anesthesia. *Computers methods and programs in biomedicine*. 2017. Vol. 147, pp. 63-83.
- Le Guen M, Liu N, Chazot T, Fischler M. Closed-loop anesthesia. *Minerva anesthesiologica*. 2016. Vol. 82, Issue 5: 573-581.

Improving the anesthetic process by a fuzzy rule based medical decision system: Highlights.

- It is possible to translate heuristic knowledge provided by clinicians into a computer system to automate drug delivery in patients undergoing general anesthesia.
- A two-level computer decision system is proposed in order to separate a supervision level and a control level.
- The proposed system performed satisfactorily in cases considered, maintaining the hypnosis level of the patient in the desired target and showing better performance parameter values than the manual standard procedure.

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Improving the anesthetic process by a fuzzy rule based medical decision system

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Abstract

Objective: The main objective of this research is the design and implementation of a new fuzzy logic tool for automatic drug delivery in patients undergoing general anesthesia. The aim is to adjust the drug dose to the real patient needs using heuristic knowledge provided by clinicians. A two-level computer decision system is proposed. The idea is to release the clinician from routine tasks so that he can focus on other variables of the patient.

Methods: The controller uses the Bispectral Index (BIS) to assess the hypnotic state of the patient. Fuzzy controller was included in a closed-loop system to reach the BIS target and reject disturbances. BIS was measured using a BIS VISTA monitor, a device capable of calculating the hypnosis level of the patient through EEG information. An infusion pump with propofol 1% is used to supply the drug to the patient. The inputs to the fuzzy inference system are BIS error and BIS rate. The output is infusion rate increment. The mapping of the input information and the appropriate output is given by a rule-base based on knowledge of clinicians.

Results: To evaluate the performance of the fuzzy closed-loop system proposed, an observational study was carried out. Eighty one patients scheduled for ambulatory surgery were randomly distributed in 2 groups: one group using a fuzzy logic based closed-loop system (FCL) to automate the administration of propofol (42 cases); the second group using manual delivering of the drug (39 cases). In both groups, the BIS target was 50.

Conclusions: The FCL, designed with intuitive logic rules based on the clinician experience, performed satisfactorily and outperformed the manual administration in patients in terms of accuracy through the maintenance stage.

Keywords: Knowledge-based system, fuzzy control, intelligent devices, drug delivery, anesthesia.

1. Introduction

In recent years, the application of computational intelligence to problems in daily life has become more common. Specifically in medicine, where health and safety of patients are involved, the number of researches related to obtain more effective results to improve traditional practices has increased. Since fuzzy set theory and fuzzy logic appeared, the

main aim has been developing decision-making systems based on human knowledge in order to apply them to some medical expert systems [1-3].

A fuzzy logic controller is a tool able to evaluate some input information in order to generate an appropriate output based on heuristic knowledge given by the experts. The appearance of this new method included important advantages to classical control engineering, using linguistic characterisation of the quality of controlled process instead of quantitative techniques based on mathematical modelling. Since the first fuzzy control application to a small steam engine [4], the use of fuzzy systems rapidly increased in several domains. Important advancements have been reached in robotic manipulators [5], in nuclear power plants [6], in automotive applications [7] or data management [8-10].

In anesthesia, the interest in automatic infusion systems comes from the expected clinical benefits of improving several aspects of the anesthetic procedure. Automatic systems based on closed-loop structures have been applied in anesthesiology in different contexts, for example, neuromuscular blockade [11], hypnosis [12-15] and analgesia control [16, 17]. In particular, systems for the administration of hypnotics using automatic procedures based on closed loop systems have been researched [18-24]. The main problem found in traditional closed loop strategies is the difficulty to tune the parameters of the controller because of the interpatient variability. Several adaptive and robust controllers have been developed in order to improve the results obtained [25, 26]. However, it is difficult to find an intuitive relationship between the parameters of the controller and the characteristics of the patient.

Using fuzzy logic to translate the clinician expertise into a controller could be an approach to solve this problem. Nevertheless, the application of fuzzy logic inference based controllers for anesthetic infusion has been less studied [27, 28]. Most researchers have

developed fuzzy controllers based on general rules that evaluate predefined situations but do not continuously consider the hypnotic state of the patient [29]. Hence, the advantages of fuzzy inference systems have not been fully exploited.

The novelty of this research is the design of a complete fuzzy inference system capable of delivering the adequate drug dose according to the hypnotic level of the patient. The rule-base has been totally designed by the clinician, taking into account all possible situations during the surgery and the appropriate actions to perform. Moreover, membership functions and the evaluated variables have been chosen following criteria of the expert. Therefore, no model is explicitly used to design the controller. The model appears implicitly through the clinician experience. As a result, this controller means a natural translation of the expertise knowledge to an automatic medical decision system.

The guidance variable to measure the hypnotic level in our study was the Bispectral Index™ (BIS), a reliable parameter that clinically correlates with the degree of hypnotic component of anesthesia [30]. BIS is a dimensionless index that varies between 100 (awake) and 0 (no electrical activity in brain). In general, a value of 50 is considered appropriate for standard surgical procedures [31]. The drug delivered in our study is propofol. The resulting system will have two functional levels: direct control level and supervision level. For the direct control level, we have developed a closed-loop controller using a Fuzzy Inference System (FIS). The supervision level is responsible to define the target to the control level, the controller setup, alarm management and communication diagnosis. On the one hand, the application of this controller would lead to an increase in patient safety, a reduction in time of use of the operating room and reduction in patient recovery time. It will be a direct consequence of adjusting the dose of drugs according to the real needs of patients. Consequently, a more accurate control of the hypnosis level could prevent the probability of adverse events [32-35]. On the other hand, this new

proposed system releases the clinician from routine tasks and allows the interaction between anesthetist and the control level.

To evaluate this method, an observational study is proposed with patients that went through ambulatory surgery. Specifically, the aim is to test the hypothesis that it is possible to translate the expertise of the clinician to a computer based system for drug automation with an improvement of the performance compared to manual administration.

2. Methods

2.1. Description of the fuzzy closed-loop system

The computer based decision system is based on a fuzzy logic controller. The objective of this system is to control the hypnosis level of the patient to reach the BIS target over time, rejecting eventual disturbances. A computer runs the fuzzy controller included in the main program developed for monitoring and controlling BIS signal. As a result, a two-level computer decision system is proposed (see figure 1).

Figure 1 General scheme of the two-level decision system proposed to control the hypnosis level of patients.

On the one hand, a closed-loop controller using a Fuzzy Inference System is designed in the direct control level. Considering the BIS target (50 in this study) and comparing it with the real level of hypnosis of patients given by BIS VISTA monitor (feedback variable), the fuzzy controller calculates the control signal. The computer communicates through a RS232 interface with the actuator, a Graseby 3500 infusion pump with propofol 1% that supplies the drug to the patient according to the control signal.

On the other hand, the supervision level makes possible the interaction between the clinician and the direct control level. The automation of the infusion pump releases the clinician from routine tasks. Consequently, the expert will be able to focus on other variables of the patient. At the supervision level it is possible to define the target of the control level and the controller setup. Moreover, the application includes an alarm module to prevent possible failures in the system (i.e. poor quality in the BIS signal) and follow established protocols to reach a secure mode (i.e. stopping the propofol infusion and commuting to manual mode). The system is periodically updated each 5 seconds.

2.2. Fuzzy-based computer decision system

From an engineering perspective, maintaining a physiological variable of interest in a desired value is accomplished by using closed-loop control structures: the controlled variable (BIS) is measured and used to calculate the adequate drug dose. This computation can be implemented using different algorithms. In this case it was done using a fuzzy inference system (FIS). A fuzzy controller is an element capable of making decisions in a closed-loop system operating in real time, based on human expert knowledge about the anesthetic process.

Firstly, to define the FIS properly it was necessary to specify the number and type of inputs and outputs to take into account. According to medical criteria, in this FIS, two input variables: BIS error (BIS_e), and BIS change (ΔBIS) and one output variable:

infusion rate increment (Δv) were considered. BIS error was computed as $BIS_e = BIS - BIS_t$ (where BIS is the measured BIS and BIS_t is the BIS target).

Fuzzy logic basis are based on fuzzy sets theory. A fuzzy set in this context is usually a generalization of the concept of interval in the real number line, extending the idea of “belonging to” to a number between 0 and 1 representing membership degree. Each variable is defined through a linguistic variable whose value can reach different linguistic values in order to describe the characteristics of both inputs and output. Let \tilde{A}_i^j denote the j^{th} linguistic value of the linguistic variable \tilde{u}_i defined over the universe of discourse U_i .

Linguistic values for variable i are represented by:

$$\tilde{A}_i = \{\tilde{A}_i^j; j = 1, 2, \dots, N_i\} \quad (1)$$

The function $\mu(u_i)$ associated with \tilde{A}_i^j that maps the universe of discourse to $[0, 1]$ is called a membership function. This membership function describes the degree of certainty that an element may be classified linguistically as \tilde{A}_i^j .

$$\mu_{\tilde{A}_i^j}(u_i) = X \rightarrow [0, 1] \quad (2)$$

A value near 1 indicates that the value is almost fully in the set, and a value near 0 indicates that the value does not belong to that set. For this FIS, triangular membership functions were defined for both inputs and output in a heuristic manner from medical experience. This choice is based on two main reasons: on the one hand, it was easier and intuitive to be modified and studied by the anesthetist, just being defined by three points; on the other hand, it was computationally more efficient. The number of membership functions for each input and output was the minimum to obtain acceptable results to achieve the target of hypnosis according to medical criteria. What is more, increasing the number of membership functions involved increasing computational time and the number of rules without improving the final result.

The distribution of the membership function along the universe of discourse was fixed by the experience of the anesthetist (see figure 2). It is important to note that, as far as the experts were concerned, the ΔBIS input did not reach any value over the ± 2 range in practice. That is why the rest of the values along the universe of discourse were saturated. In addition, an “emergence situation” was defined for the Δv output as an isolated membership function whether ΔBIS were highly negative or BIS reached any value under safety limits predefined. As a result, a considerable decrement was desirable in these cases.

Figure 2 Input and output fuzzy partitions of the fuzzy logic controller. Top: membership functions for BIS Error input. Middle: membership functions for the Increment of BIS input. Bottom: membership functions for infusion rate increment output.

If we consider a fuzzy controller with crisp inputs (*BISe*, Δ *BIS*), it is necessary to turn them into a fuzzy value in order to associate them with membership functions of inputs. In this case, to develop the fuzzification process, a singleton fuzzification method was used. Then, the mapping of the inputs to the output is characterised by *if-then* rules.

$$\text{IF } u_1 \text{ is } A^1_i, \text{ AND } u_2 \text{ is } A^2_i, \text{ AND } \dots \text{ and } u_n \text{ is } A^n_i, \text{ THEN } y \text{ is } B_i \quad (3)$$

For this purpose, the set of logical rules will be expressed as:

$$\text{If } BISe \text{ is } A \text{ and } \Delta BIS \text{ is } B \text{ then } \Delta v \text{ is } C, \quad (4)$$

where *A*, *B* and *C* are linguistic terms describing levels of the corresponding variable value. The entire set of the linguistic rules is the way to specify how to control the system through expert knowledge. To design the rules considered in this FIS, the following process was developed:

- Firstly, it was necessary to study and analyse data from thirty patients undergoing manual general anesthesia. It was possible to design a previous rule base according to the relation among both inputs and output.
- Secondly, anesthetists validated previous rule base and completed it with all possible combinations between inputs following expert knowledge.

The rule base considered in the studied FIS is shown in table 1.

To evaluate each rule, it was necessary to match every fuzzy set obtained from the fuzzification with membership functions of the inputs. The process to obtain conclusions from inputs and rule base is called inference. In this FIS, a Mamdani inference system was developed. As singleton fuzzification was used, the certainty that the *i*-th rule's premise matches the input information is represented by

$$\mu_i(u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n) = \mu_{A^1_i}(u_1) * \mu_{A^2_i}(u_2) * \dots * \mu_{A^n_i}(u_n), \quad (5)$$

where the product operation “*” is implemented using the *min* operator. The result of the inference for the *i*-th rule is the fuzzy set \hat{B}_i defined by the membership function:

$$\mu_{\hat{B}_i}(y) = \mu_i(u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n) * \mu_{B_i}(y) \quad (6)$$

Finally, in order to obtain a numerical value of the output coherently with the rule base and the generalisation provided by the fuzzy logic framework, a defuzzification process was performed. The centre of area method is used, computing the numerical output value as:

$$y = \left(\sum_{i=1}^R b_i \int_y \mu_{\hat{B}_i}(y) dy \right) / \left(\sum_{i=1}^R \int_y \mu_{\hat{B}_i}(y) dy \right), \quad (7)$$

where b_i is the centre of area of the resulting output membership function of rule *i* ($\mu_{\hat{B}_i}(y)$) and $\int_y \mu_{\hat{B}_i}(y) dy$ is the area under the function $\mu_{\hat{B}_i}(y)$.

As a result, the rule base is a linguistic representation of a receipt to respond to variations in the BIS value by increasing or decreasing the propofol infusion rate. The linguistic representation is a key difference between this FIS and other types of controller, for example Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID) algorithms, because it provides the designer with the additional advantage of being able to discuss improvements in the controller operation with the field expert, in this case the anesthesiologist, in terms of intuitive rules.

Moreover, a FIS includes the mechanisms to work with numerical values in the input to produce numerical values in the output coherently with the rule base and the generalization provided by the fuzzy logic framework. Therefore, the whole system consists of three stages: fuzzification, inference and defuzzification (see figure 3).

Detailed description of FIS operation is given by Lee [36, 37].

Figure 3 Basic components and stages of a fuzzy inference system.

A global scheme of the control system shown in figure 4 is a closed-loop structure where the controller computes the appropriate dose according to the BIS signal and its variation. The final result of the controller behaviour is shown through response surface in figure 5.

Figure 4 Automatic administration of propofol with a fuzzy closed loop. Controlled variable is BIS. The inputs of the fuzzy inference system are BIS error and BIS change rate. Controller output is infusion rate change.

Figure 5 Response surface of the fuzzy controller for the anesthetic control task representing the value of increment infusion rate according to $BISe(t)$ and $\Delta BIS(t)$ values.

2.3. Design of the observational study

To evaluate the performance of the fuzzy closed-loop system proposed, an observational study was carried out with 85 patients that went through ambulatory surgery. The surgical procedures chosen were gynaecological, vascular and general surgery. The propofol was infused by means of an automatic device operated by the fuzzy inference system in a group of patients (FCL group). For the rest of patients (control group), the method was the standard manual administration of propofol by an experienced anesthesiologist.

Inclusion criteria were: ASA I-II, age 18-80 years and general anesthesia. Criteria of exclusion were: refusal by the patient, $ASA \geq III$, a psychiatric or neurological disorder

or the presence of a pacemaker. Four patients were finally excluded from the study, one patient in the FCL group due to a haemorrhage at the end of the surgery and 3 patients due to protocol violations, one in the FCL group and two in the control group.

In this case, we have tried to obviate the interaction of opiates to the fullest maintaining a constant perfusion of remifentanyl. This also could represent a more stable BIS signal when assessing performance of the controller. Published studies on this interaction [38] set margins where the addition of remifentanyl does not introduce changes in its pharmacokinetic or pharmacodynamics behaviour. For this study a moderate remifentanyl dose was used in order to obtain an acceptable range of interaction level with propofol.

2.4. Statistical Analysis

To quantify the performance of the controller, a statistical analysis was developed. Performance Error (PE) is a per sample measurement giving the percentage of deviation from the target BIS. The MDPE (MDPAE) is a per case measurement giving the median of PE (absolute value of PE) in the maintenance stage. The wobble gives the information of intra-individual variability in performance errors. It is defined for i case as:

$$Wobble_i = \text{Median} \{ |PE_{ij} - MDPE_i|, j=1 \dots N_i \}, \quad (8)$$

where i = subject number, j = j^{th} (one) measurement of observation period and N = total number of measurements during the observation period.

The global score (GS) is given by:

$$GS_i = (MDAPE_i + Wobble_i) / PBIS4060_i, \quad (9)$$

where $PBIS4060_i$ is the percentage of time when BIS value is set in the target band (BIS within 40-60 range) during maintenance stage for case i .

Finally, clinical performance parameters represent the percentage of time of the maintenance stage with the BIS value in a particular band. In this study the proposed bands were: excellent (45-55 range), good (40-45 and 55-60), poor (<40 and >60) divided into undershooting (BIS >60) and overshooting (BIS < 40).

In this paper, results are presented for the main performance measurements using mean value, standard deviation and 95% confidence intervals. The Mann-Whitney U-test was applied to obtain a p-value to assess how strongly we can reject the null hypothesis that the medians of the responses in the fuzzy logic based closed-loop system (FCL) group and in the control group are similar.

Data analysis has been carried out with the statistical software R (a Language and Environment for Statistical Computing (R Core Team)). Distribution of sample values were also described using box-and-whisker plots provided by the R software. The box represents the median, the first quantile Q1 and the third quantile Q3. The whiskers outside the box represent the extremes of the distribution excluding the outliers. A point is considered an outlier if it is separated from the box more than the inter-quantile range: $IQR=1.5 \cdot (Q3 - Q1)$.

3. Results

This study was approved by the Clinical Research Ethics Committee of “Hospital Universitario de Canarias”. Written informed consent was obtained from all subjects enrolled in the study. The results were obtained from 81 patients (42 in the FCL group and 39 in the control group) whose ages, Body Mass Index (BMI) and sex are summarized in table 2. Regression analysis using as response variables the main studied parameters (MDAPE, global score, excellent, good, and poor performance, undershoot and overshoot

bands) revealed that these confounding variables were not significantly influencing the results.

Remifentanyl infusion was administered according to the clinical protocol in 72 patients. In the remaining 9 cases (7 in the manual control group and 2 in the FCL group), there was a need for a transient increase in the remifentanyl rate by up to 0.25 mcg/kg/min. The induction phase was similar in both groups. The controller was able to correct eventual deviations of the BIS caused by surgical stimulus. No significant adverse effect was reported in any group. The incidence of hypertension or hypotension was not significant and no differences were observed between groups.

General aspects of the surgical procedure are summarized in table 3, where duration of anesthesia, time to open eyes once surgery has finished, and propofol consumption are compared for FCL group and control group. There were no significant differences except for propofol consumption that was slightly higher in the FCL group than in the control group (5.69mg/kg/h vs 4.53mg/kg/h). It was due to a better adaptation of the supply of drug according to hypnosis level of patients. Therefore, a slightly shorter time to open eyes once surgery has finished was obtained in the FCL group than in the control group (6.81 min vs 7.51 min).

Figure 6 shows the behaviour of the BIS variable for a particular case in the FCL group. Observe that the surgical procedure started with a bolus infusion calculated taking into account the characteristics of patient. Subsequently, the BIS level decreased until it reached the appropriate value to start the automatic control task. The BIS deviations from the target value were corrected increasing or decreasing the propofol infusion rate according to the rule base defined in the fuzzy controller. As a result, BIS values near BIS target were obtained during the process. The evolution of median, 10th and 90th percentile

values for the 42 patients in the FCL group once the automatic control task started are also shown in Figure 7.

Figure 6 BIS and propofol infusion rate with the fuzzy closed loop in the maintenance stage for one of the patients. The propofol infusion rate is being automatically adjusted to keep the BIS near a target value of 50.

Figure 7. Evolution of median, 10th and 90th percentile values for the 42 patients in the FCL group once the automatic control task started.

The analytical results based on clinical performance parameters are shown in table 4. They represent the percentage of the maintenance stage with the BIS in the excellent, good, poor, overshooting and undershooting bands. The results in the FCL group significantly improved the corresponding ones in the control group. Specifically, percentage of time spent in the excellent band for FCL group reached over 50% of total maintenance time, while the percentage in this band for control group did not reach 40%. Despite of these results, the percentage of time in undershooting band was in favour of the control group, however, the difference was not statistically significant. These results are also graphically represented in figure 8 showing the box-and-whisker plots for the excellent, good and poor bands.

Figure 8 Box-and-whisker plots representing the clinical performance for excellent, good and poor levels. The variable studied for the FCL group and the control group is the percentage of time with the BIS in the 10% (excellent), between 10% and 20% (good) and over 20% (poor) of the target value. In this study the target value is 50.

Finally, table 5 represents parameters related to the performance of the controller. The results for the MDPE, MDAPE and global score parameters showed a significant contrast between both groups in favour of the FCL group. According to MDPE and MDAPE values, the differences between real BIS of patient and BIS target during the process are lower in FCL group than in control group. In addition, the MDAPE standard deviation

showed more spread out values in control group than in the FCL group. This is another evidence of the tendency of the automated system to keep the BIS very close to the target value. In particular, the global score shows an important improvement when the automated system is used: 22.78 for the FCL group and 32.28 for the control group. The box-and-whisker plots of these results are shown in figure 9.

The analysis of the performance of the FCL was completed by comparing the results with other efficient methods developed. The same parameters related to the performance of the controller were used to compare them. The results of this comparison also demonstrated the potential of our technique, improving percentage of time in the excellent band as well as reducing the MDAPE coefficient. A detailed description of the comparison is included in Discussion section.

Figure 9 Box-and-whisker plots for MDPE, MDAPE, Wobble and global score. In the global score panel several outliers are not shown in the figure. The complete list of outliers for global scores are 49.9, 55.1 and 69.7 for the FCL group and 53.4, 53.9, 58.58, 109.34 and 121.5 for the control group.

4. Discussion

An automated system has been developed for hypnosis control based on logic reasoning with linguistic terms that has been used in ambulatory surgery patients. The system is based on a two-level decision architecture. The lowest level uses a fuzzy controller, a

methodology widely used for automation and control in the industry. The novelty in our work is the use of a controller that can incorporate the expertise of the anesthetist. The proposed system performed satisfactorily in all cases maintaining the hypnosis level of the patient in the desired target and showing better performance parameter values than the manual standard procedure. Neither adverse events, nor awaking episodes were observed.

Fuzzy logic has been considered in anesthesia control by few authors. Moore et al. [39] proposed a simulated controller based on fuzzy rules. The study of Janda et al. [27] also considered the use of fuzzy methodologies. However, they used a different controller structure based on the implementation of a PID where the main mathematical calculations are replaced by a fuzzy model. The system described here differs from these proposals in how the controller is designed, in this case by means of the direct knowledge provided by clinicians.

Fuzzy controllers have been also applied to the control of neuromuscular blockade. Fazendeiro [40] proposed a new solution based on a fuzzy logic controller for neuromuscular blockade with atracurium. Although a good performance was reached in simulation, there are some differences that must be taken into account. From the clinical point of view, it is easier to measure the effects of atracurium by noninvasive methods (TOF or kinemyography) than the hypnotic effects in patients [41]. In addition, the objective proposed in Fazendeiro's research is slightly different. Using different optimization strategies, it is aimed not only the development of a controller but also the design of a decision rule based protocol to explain the undertaken control decision behind the neuromuscular blockade process. Unlike Fazendeiro's, our research considered the heuristic knowledge previously obtained from the expertise of clinicians as a starting point, and then it is applied to the development of the FLC structure. As a result, the

proposed controller takes advantage of the main purpose of fuzzy logic theory: translation of the knowledge in a natural language into an automatic algorithm capable of being managed by clinicians.

Hemmerling et al [18] and Liu et al [19] developed PID based systems to control hypnotic state of patients. Hemmerling et al proposed that the given dose of propofol is calculated based on $Dose_{prop} = previousDose_{prop} \cdot K_m \cdot K_h$. K_m is proportional to the difference between actual BIS and the target proposed and K_h is proportional to the difference of the mean BIS to the target over the last time interval. Liu et al proposed a standard PID structure, whose parameters were determined empirically using a simulator based on pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamics models.

We are going to proceed to compare the results obtained with fuzzy logic controller and the results obtained by Liu and Hemmerling. However, it is important to notice that there exist several differences in the development of the researches that must be taken into account. The main difference is the type of patients included in the studies: while in this study we are including ASA I/II patients, Hemmerling et al. included ASA I/II/III patients and Liu et al. ASA III/IV patients. Moreover, the type of surgery studied is different. This difference has an impact in the duration of anesthesia: Hemmerling et al. report 195 (86) (178-122) minutes for his closed loop system and 191 (95) (172-211) minutes for his control group, and Liu et al. report for the maintenance stage 140 (78) minutes for his closed loop system and 150 (81) (89-188) minutes for his control group. As shown in table 3, the duration of the cases studied in this research is significantly shorter: 48.70 (39.39) (36.42-60.97) minutes for the closed loop system and 54.02 (18.88) (47.90-60.15) minutes for the control group. Notice that shorter maintenance stages make it more difficult to obtain good values for parameters representing stability of the BIS signal.

However, as it is shown in table 6, several of our results improved the ones reported by Hemmerling et al. and Liu et al. while in some other cases the performance was similar. Another difference comes from the definition of BIS target and the ranges of bands. Liu et al. proposed the same BIS target of 50, although excellent and good band were not considered separately, but in a single band. Hemmerling et al. use a lower BIS target of 45, changing the definition of the bands. Consequently, the results obtained should be compared taking these facts into account.

Table 6 and table 7 show the main results of these three closed loop systems and the control group in each case. For the obtained percentage of time in the excellent band, it is shown that the time spent in excellent and good band for the fuzzy closed loop we proposed was slightly better than the results obtained by Liu (82.2% vs 82%). What is more, as it is shown in table 7, the MDAPE coefficient, relative to the error between BIS target and real BIS, for the fuzzy closed loop controller proposed was lower than the coefficient obtained by Liu (9.7 vs 11.4). The lower standard deviation for the controller we proposed against the controller proposed by Liu (3 vs 4.3) is another evidence of the tendency of our system to keep the BIS closer to the target value. It means that the fuzzy inference based controller offers a better accuracy than the PID based systems in the target band. As a result, a better global score was obtained again for fuzzy controller in comparison to the PID controller proposed by Liu (22.8 vs 26) (see table 7).

Table 6 shows that although overshooting behaviour ($BIS < 40$) was also better for our controller than in Liu et al [19] (11.2% vs 15%), undershooting considered when $BIS > 60$ was worse for the fuzzy logic controller (6.6%) than the results obtained by Hemmerling (1.9%) and by Liu (3%). Notice that a relevant part of this difference in the undershooting band results could be explained by the shorter duration of the maintenance stage in our study. Hemmerling et al. are reporting the lowest undershooting band percentage, but

notice that they are using a lower BIS target that makes it more difficult for patients to reach the undershooting band (BIS>60).

As a result, the proposed system based on knowledge of experts outperformed traditional controllers based on PID closed-loop systems, especially when comparing the time of BIS index in the excellent band. Our system totally exploits the benefits of fuzzy logic systems, so that it is fully design by anesthetists. Fuzzy system is able to consider all possible situations related to hypnotic state of patient during surgery through the rule base defined, calculating the propofol dose as anesthetists would. Moreover, the main characteristics of our controller are not based on the theoretical models as the controllers proposed by Hemmerling or Liu. The model appears implicitly through the clinician experience. Consequently, due to a proper adjustment of the propofol dose according to the real needs of patients, our controller would increase the safety of patients, preventing the probability of adverse events, as well as reducing the time of use of the operating room and reducing recovery time.

5. Conclusions

The observational study together with this comparative analysis revealed a robust performance of the fuzzy inference based controller guided by BIS. The researched system outperformed manual control and when compared to other controllers it offers several improvements, mainly related to maintaining the BIS in the excellent band. These results evidence that it is feasible to develop an automated infusion system using a fuzzy inference controller designed from intuitive logical rules for the control algorithm. This allows the clinician to actively take part in the design of the automatic infusion system and to adapt it to clinical requirements of the specific surgery. With this, the clinician will

avoid the continuous interaction with the infusion pump and will be focused mainly on the supervision level.

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References

1. Nguyen HP, Kreinovich V. Fuzzy logic and its applications in medicine. *International Journal of medical informatics*. July 2001. Volume 62, Issues 2-3, 165-173.
2. Mahfouf M, Abbod MF, Linkens DA. A survey of fuzzy logic monitoring and control utilisation in medicine. *Artificial Intelligence in Medicine*. 2001. Volume 21, Issue 1 , 27 – 42.
3. Pota M, Esposito M, De Pietro G. Designing rule-based fuzzy systems for classification in medicine. *Knowledge-based Systems*. 2017. Volume 124. 105-132.
4. Precup RE, Hellendoorn H. A survey of industrial applications of fuzzy control. *Computers in Industry*. 2011. Volume 62, Issue 3: 213-226.
5. De Silva, CW. Applications of fuzzy logic in the control of robotic manipulators. *Fuzzy Sets and Systems*. 1995. Volume 70, Issue 2-3: 223-234.
6. Brown C, Gabbar HA. Fuzzy logic control for improved pressurizer systems in nuclear power plants. *Annals of Nuclear Energy*. 2014. Volume 72. 461-466.
7. Altrock CV, Krause B, Zimmermann HJ. Advanced fuzzy logic control technologies in automotive applications. *IEEE International Conference on Fuzzy Systems, 1992*. 835-842.
8. Alhabashneh O, Iqbal R, Doctor F, Amin S. Adaptive Information Retrieval System Based on Fuzzy Profiling. *IEEE International Conference on Fuzzy Systems*. 2015.
9. Alhabashneh O, Iqbal, R, Doctor, F. Fuzzy Rule Based Profiling Approach For Enterprise Information Seeking and Retrieval. *Information Sciences* 2016.
10. Mahmud S, Iqbal R, Doctor F. Cloud enabled data analytics and visualization

- framework for health-shocks prediction. *Journal of Future Generation of Computer Systems* 2016. Vol 65, pp. 169–181.
11. Mason DG, Edwards ND, Linkens DA, Reilly CS. Performance assessment of a fuzzy controller for atracurium-induced neuromuscular block. *British journal of anaesthesia* 1996;76:396–400.
 12. Schwilden H, Stoeckel H, Schüttler J. Closed-loop feedback control of propofol anaesthesia by quantitative EEG analysis in humans. *British journal of anaesthesia* 1989;62:290–6.
 13. Arıkan FGO, Turan G, Ozgultekin A, Sivrikaya Z, Cosar BC, Onder DN. Rocuronium: automatic infusion versus manual administration with TOF monitorisation. *Journal of Clinical Monitoring and Computing*. 2016. Vol. 30, Issue 5: 545-550.
 14. Padula F, Ionescu C, Latronico N, Paltenghi M, Visioli A, Vivacqua G. Optimized PID control of depth of hypnosis in anesthesia. *Computer Methods and Programs in Biomedicine*. 2017. Vol.144, pp. 21-35.
 15. Hemmerling TM, Charabati S, Zaouter C, Minardi C, Mathieu PA. A randomized controlled trial demonstrates that a novel closed-loop propofol system performs better hypnosis control than manual administration. *Canadian journal of anaesthesia = Journal canadien d'anesthésie* 2010;57:725–35. doi:10.1007/s12630-010-9335-z.
 16. Gentilini A, Schaniel C, Morari M, Bieniok C, Wymann R, Schnider T. A new paradigm for the closed-loop intraoperative administration of analgesics in humans. *IEEE transactions on bio-medical engineering* 2002;49:289–99. doi:10.1109/10.991156.
 17. Hemmerling TM, Charabati S, Salhab E. The Analgoscore TM : a novel score to

- monitor intraoperative nociception and its use for closed-loop application of remifentanyl. *Anesthesiology* 2009;4:311–318. doi:10.4304/jcp.4.4.311-318.
18. Hemmerling TM, Arbeid E, Wehbe M, et al. Evaluation of a novel closed-loop total intravenous anaesthesia drug delivery system: A randomized controlled trial. *British Journal of Anaesthesia* 2013;110:1031–1039.
 19. Liu N, Chazot T, Hamada S, et al. Closed-loop coadministration of propofol and remifentanyl guided by bispectral index: A randomized multicenter study. *Anesthesia and Analgesia* 2011;112:546–557.
 20. Absalom AR, Kenny GNC. Closed-loop control of propofol anaesthesia using bispectral index TM: Performance assessment in patients receiving computer-controlled propofol and manually controlled remifentanyl infusions for minor surgery. *British Journal of Anaesthesia* 2003;90:737–741.
 21. Sawaguchi Y, Furutani E, Shirakami G, Araki M, Fukuda K. A model-predictive hypnosis control system under total intravenous anesthesia. *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering* 2008;55:874–887.
 22. Rebozo J a., Méndez J a., Rebozo HJ, León a. M. Design and implementation of a closed-loop control system for infusion of propofol guided by bispectral index (BIS). *Acta Anaesthesiologica Scandinavica* 2012;56:1032–1041. doi:10.1111/j.1399-6576.2012.02738.x.
 23. Méndez JA, Torres S, Rebozo JA, Rebozo H. Adaptive computer control of anesthesia in humans. *Computer methods in biomechanics and biomedical engineering* 2009;12:727–734.
 24. Merigo L, Beschi M, Padula F, Latronico N, Paltenghi M, Visioli A. Event-Based control of depth of hypnosis in anesthesia. *Computers methods and programs in biomedicine*. 2017. Vol. 147, pp. 63-83.

25. Van Heusden K, Dumont GA, Soltesz K, Petersen CL, Umedaly A, West N, Ansermino JM. Design and clinical evaluation of robust PID control of propofol anesthesia in children. *IEEE Trans. Control Syst. Technol.* 2014, vol 22, no. 2, pp. 491-501.
26. Dineva A, Tar, JK, Várkonyi-Kóczy A, Piuri V. Adaptive controller using fixed point transformation for regulating propofol administration through wavelet-based anesthetic value. 2016 IEEE International Symposium on Medical Measurements and Applications. Benevento, 2016, pp. 1-6.
27. Janda M, Simanski O, Bajorat J, Pohl B, Noeldge-Schomburg GFE, Hofmockel R. Clinical evaluation of a simultaneous closed-loop anaesthesia control system for depth of anaesthesia and neuromuscular blockade. *Anaesthesia* 2011;66:1112–1120.
28. Doctor F, Syue CH, Shieh JH, Iqbal R. Type-2 Fuzzy Sets Applied to Multivariable Self-Organizing Fuzzy Logic Controllers for Regulating Anesthesia. *Journal of Applied Soft Computing* 2016. Vol 38, pp. 872–889.
29. Shieh JS, Linkens DA, Peacock JE. Hierarchical rule based and self-organizing fuzzy logic control for control depth of anaesthesia. *IEEE Trans. Syst. Man. Cybern.-Part C*, vol 29, pp. 98-109, 1999.
30. Bonhomme V, Hans P. Monitoring depth of anaesthesia: is it worth the effort? *European journal of anaesthesiology* 2004; 21:423–8.
31. Dumont GA, Ansermino JM. Closed-loop control of anesthesia: a primer for anesthesiologists. *Anesthesia and Analgesia* 2013; 117:1130-1138.
32. Leslie K, Short TG. Low bispectral index values and death: the unresolved causality dilemma. *Anesth Analg* 2011; 113:660–663. doi:10.1213/ANE.0b013e31822401cc113/3/660 [pii].

33. Lindholm ML, Träff S, Granath F, et al. Mortality within 2 years after surgery in relation to low intraoperative bispectral index values and preexisting malignant disease. *Anesthesia and Analgesia* 2009;108:508–512.
34. Leslie K, Myles PS, Forbes A, Chan MT V. The effect of bispectral index monitoring on long-term survival in the B-aware trial. *Anesthesia and Analgesia* 2010;110:816–822.
35. Kertai MD, Pal N, Palanca BJA, et al. Association of perioperative risk factors and cumulative duration of low bispectral index with intermediate-term mortality after cardiac surgery in the B-Unaware Trial. *Anesthesiology* 2010;112:1116–27. doi:10.1097/ALN.0b013e3181d5e0a3.
36. Lee CCC. Fuzzy logic in control systems: fuzzy logic controller. II. *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics* 1990;20:404–418. doi:10.1109/21.52551.
37. Lee CC. Fuzzy logic in control systems: fuzzy logic controller - Part 1. *IEEE Transactions On Systems Man And Cybernetics* 1990;20:419–435. doi:10.1109/21.52552.
38. Bouillon TW, Bruhn J, Radulescu L, et al. Pharmacodynamic interaction between propofol and remifentanyl regarding hypnosis, tolerance of laryngoscopy, bispectral index, and electroencephalographic approximate entropy. *Anesthesiology* 2004;100:1353–1372.
39. Moore BL, Pyeatt LD, Doufas AG. Fuzzy control for closed-loop, patient-specific hypnosis in intraoperative patients: A simulation study. In: *Proceedings of the 31st Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society: Engineering the Future of Biomedicine, EMBC 2009*; 2009:3083–3086.

40. Fazendeiro P, de Oliveira JV, Pedrycz W. A multiobjective design of a patient and anaesthetist-friendly neuromuscular blockade controller. *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering*. 2007. Vol. 54, Issue 9: 1667-1678.
41. Le Guen M, Liu N, Chazot T, Fischler M. Closed-loop anesthesia. *Minerva anesthesiologica*. 2016. Vol. 82, Issue 5: 573-581.

TABLES

Table 1 Rule base of the fuzzy inference system. Each rule is a clause of type: “if *BIS_e* and ΔBIS then Δv ” where antecedent variables are the BIS error (*BIS_e*) and the BIS change (ΔBIS). The rule consequent is the change in propofol infusion rate (Δv).

# Rule	<i>BIS_e</i>	ΔBIS	Δv
1	Highly Negative	--	Very important decrease
2	Negative	Highly Negative	Very important decrease
3	Negative	Negative	Decrease
4	Negative	Medium	Decrease
5	Negative	Positive	Maintain
6	Negative	Highly Positive	Increase
7	Medium	Highly Negative	Important decrease
8	Medium	Negative	Decrease
9	Medium	Medium	Maintain
10	Medium	Positive	Increase
11	Medium	Highly Positive	Increase
12	Positive	Highly Negative	Maintain
13	Positive	Negative	Increase
14	Positive	Medium	Increase
15	Positive	Positive	Increase
16	Positive	Highly Positive	Important Increase
17	Highly Positive	Highly Negative	Maintain
18	Highly Positive	Negative	Increase
19	Highly Positive	Medium	Important Increase
20	Highly Positive	Positive	Important Increase
21	Highly Positive	Highly Positive	Important Increase

Table 2 Summary of patient information. Age, weight and Body Mass Index (BMI) is presented as mean (Standard Deviation) (95% Confidence Interval). First column refers to the proposal of this study (Fuzzy Logic based Closed-loop system) applied to 42 patients and second column presents results obtained using manual administration in 39 patients. P-values are derived from Mann-Whitney U-test.

	FCL Group (n=42)	Control Group (n=39)	p value
Age; years	38.21 (14.89) (33.57-42.86)	46.41 (14.93) (41.57-51.25)	0.0183
Weight; kg	68.88 (12.89) (64.86-72.90)	73.72 (13.69) (69.28-78.16)	0.1387
BMI	24.22 (3.75) (23.05-25.39)	25.99 (4.59) (24.51-27.48)	0.0492
Sex (M/F)	16/26	21/18	0.1592

Table 3 General information about the anesthetic process in patients. Duration of anesthesia, time to open eyes once surgery has finished and propofol consumption is presented as mean value (Standard Deviation) (95% Confidence Interval). First column refers to the proposal of this study (Fuzzy Logic based Closed-loop system) applied to 42 patients and second column presents results obtained using manual administration in 39 patients. P-values are derived from Mann-Whitney U-test.

	FCL Group (n= 42)	Control Group (n= 39)	p value
Anesthesia duration; min	48.70 (39.39) (36.42- 60.97)	54.02 (18.88) (47.90- 60.15)	0.0136
Time to open eyes; min	6.81 (3.19) (5.82-7.80)	7.51 (3.22) (6.46-8.55)	0.4580
Propofol consumption; mg/kg/h	5.69 (2.02) (5.06-6.32)	4.53 (1.06) (4.19-4.87)	0.0019

Table 4 Study of the clinical performance. Percentage of time spent in the excellent, good, poor, overshoot and undershoot bands for the FCL group and control group. Values are mean (Standard Deviation) (95% Confidence Interval). P-values are derived from Mann-Whitney U-test.

	FCL Group (n= 42)	Control Group (n= 39)	p value
Excellent	53.09 (12.02) (49.34-56.83)	37.62 (15.94) (32.45-42.78)	0.000031
Good	29.10 (6.82) (26.98-31.23)	38.01 (11.65) (34.23-41.78)	0.00031
Poor	17.81 (10.59) (14.51 -21.11)	24.38 (15.98) (19.19-29.56)	0.0748
Overshoot	11.22 (8.54) (8.56-13.88)	19.52 (14.43) (14.84-24.19)	0.0032
Undershoot	6.6 (7.4) (4.3-8.9)	4.9 (6.7) (2.7-7.0)	0.2299

Table 5 Study about the controller performance. Information for MDPE, MDAPE, Wobble, and Global Score is given as mean (Standard Deviation) (95% Confidence Interval). P-values are derived from Mann-Whitney U-test. MDPE, median performance error; MDAPE, median absolute performance error.

	FCL Group (n=42)	Control Group (n=39)	p value
MDPE	-3.13 (4.95) (-4.67- (-1.59))	-9.83 (7.11) (-12.14- (-7.52))	6.5 10 ⁻⁶
MDAPE	9.67 (3.02) (8.73-10.61)	13.50 (4.43) (12.07-14.94)	8.8 10 ⁻⁵
Wobble	8.55 (3.31) (7.51-9.58)	7.63 (3.08) (6.63-8.63)	0.2017
Global Score	22.78 (12.25) (18.97-26.60)	32.28 (22.61) (24.95-39.61)	0.0072

Table 6 Comparative study of the performance bands between the proposed fuzzy inference system, Hemmerling et al [18] and Liu et al [19]. Percentage of time is obtained on the maintenance stage. Results are given as mean (standard deviation) (95 % confidence interval). P-value is the result of Mann-Whitney U-test. Notice the different definitions for performance bands and BIS target. C, control; CL, Closed Loop group;

	Fuzzy Closed Loop Target BIS=50	Hemmerling et al Target BIS=45	Liu et al Target BIS=50
N° of cases (Closed Loop /Control)	42/39	93/93	83/84
Excellent Band (EB)			
Definition	$ BIS-50 \leq 5$	$ BIS-45 \leq 4.5$	Excellent and
% Time in EB (CL)	53.1 (12.0) (49.3-56.8)	47(9.8) (45.0-49.0)	good bands are
% Time in EB (C)	37.6 (15.9) (32.4-42.8)	37.3(14.3) (34.4-40.2)	considered in a
p value	$<10^{-4}$	$<10^{-4}$	single band
Good Band (GB)			
Definition	$5 < BIS-50 \leq 10$	$4.5 < BIS-45 \leq 9$	$ BIS-50 \leq 10$
% Time in GB (CL)	29.1 (6.8) (27.0-31.2)	34.4(4.7) (33.5-35.4)	82(12.85) (73-91)
% Time in GB (C)	38.0 (11.6) (34.2-41.8)	32.3(7.6) (30.7-33.7)	71(19.8) (59-85)
P-value	0.0003	0.008	$<10^{-4}$
Overshoot (O)			
Definition	$BIS < 40$	$BIS < 35$	$BIS < 40$
% Time in O (CL)	11.2 (8.5) (8.6-13.9)	10.6 (8.5) (8.9-12.3)	15 (11) (6-22)
% Time in O (C)	19.5 (14.4) (14.8-24.2)	20.5 (14.7) (17.5-23.5)	24 (21) (7-39)
p value	0.0032	$<10^{-4}$	0.016
Undershoot (U)			
Definition	$BIS > 60$	$BIS > 60$	$BIS > 60$
% Time in U (CL)	6.6 (7.4) (4.3-8.9)	1.9(2.1) (1.5-2.3)	3(4) (0-3)
% Time in U (C)	4.9 (6.7) (2.7-7.0)	3.4(4.5) (2.5-4.3)	5(7.2) (0-6)
p value	0.23	0.0051	0.031

Table 7 Comparative study of the controller performance between the proposed fuzzy inference system, Hemmerling et al [18] and Liu et al [19]. Results are given as mean (standard deviation) (95 % confidence interval). P-value is the result of Mann-Whitney U-test. Notice that Hemmerling et al [18] take a BIS target of 45, while a BIS target of 50 is taken in the other cases. C, control; CL, Closed Loop group; MDAPE, median absolute performance error.

	Fuzzy Closed Loop Target BIS=50	Hemmerling et al Target BIS=45	Liu et al Target BIS=50
N° of cases (Closed Loop /Control)	42/39	93/93	83/84
MDAPE (CL)	9.7 (3.0) (8.7-10.6)	11.0(2.6) (10.5-11.5)	11.4(4.3) (9.0-14.0)
MDAPE (C)	13.5 (4.4)	15.4(10.4)	15.0(5.5) (11.5-18.0)
p value	<10 ⁻⁴	<10 ⁻⁴	<10 ⁻⁴
Global Score (CL)	22.8 (12.3) (19.0-26.6)	-	26(11) (19-30)
Global Score (C)	32.3 (22.6) (25.0-39.6)	-	43(40) (24-49)
p value	0.0072	-	<10 ⁻⁴

BIS

Propofol infusion

% of excellent performance

% of good performance

% of poor performance

MDPE

MDAPE

Wobble

Global score

